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RESEARCH ARTICLE

O-RAN-Enabled Adaptive Relaying for Robust V2X Communication in Urban NLOS Scenarios

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ABSTRACT The Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) introduces programmability and intelligence into wireless infrastructure, making it a promising enabler of reliable Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication in complex urban environments. Unlike traditional RAN, O-RAN's disaggregated architecture and RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) allow real-time adaptation to Non-Line-of-Sight (NLOS) challenges, an issue unresolved in many existing V2X systems. This paper proposes an adaptive relaying framework that leverages the near-real-time RIC to dynamically enhance V2X reliability through dynamic relay selection and interference-aware resource coordination. The architecture supports programmable fallback relaying using disaggregated Distributed Unit (O-DU)/Radio Unit (O-RU) at roadside infrastructure, enabling low-latency two-hop paths when direct sidelink communication fails. To evaluate performance, a semi-analytical model based on Moment Matching Approximation (MMA) is developed, capturing the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) under composite Nakagami-lognormal fading and stochastic co-channel interference. The framework integrates O-RAN with NR-V2X sidelink communication to bridge the gap between centralized and ad-hoc vehicular networks. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed O-RAN-aided relaying improves Packet Success Probability (PSP) in dense NLOS scenarios, consistently achieving a PSP above 90%. The framework outperforms conventional LOS and NLOS approaches while maintaining compatibility with 3GPP Release 18 and O-RAN Alliance specifications, ensuring practical deployability in future intelligent transportation systems (ITS).

INDEX TERMS O-RAN, NR-V2X, sidelink communication, RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), NLOS, adaptive relaying, fallback mechanism, packet success probability (PSP), 3GPP Release 18.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reliable Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication is a foundational pillar of future Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), enabling seamless interaction among vehicles (V2V), infrastructure (V2I), pedestrians (V2P), and networks (V2N). These interactions enhance road safety,

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reduce traffic congestion, and support automated driving functionalities. In urban environments, however, V2X faces critical challenges due to dynamic topologies, dense vehicle deployments, and frequent signal obstructions that impair connectivity.

To address these issues, the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) introduced 5G New Radio Vehicle-to-Everything (NR-V2X), which supports ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) and scalable sidelink

access in high-density deployments [1], [2], [3], [4]. Nevertheless, urban Non-Line-of-Sight (NLOS) conditions remain a major bottleneck, resulting in unpredictable reliability due to multipath fading, shadowing, and constrained channel reuse.

Emerging enhancements such as Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) and cooperative relaying attempt to alleviate NLOS limitations by reshaping the propagation environment or by introducing alternate relay paths [5], [6], [7]. However, these techniques often rely on static infrastructure or simplified models that fail to adapt in real time to high vehicular density scenarios. Moreover, they typically lack integration with intelligent control-plane functions necessary for dynamic resource management.

Traditional Radio Access Network (RAN) architectures compound the problem by depending on centralized and rigid control, which cannot respond efficiently to fast-varying interference patterns or link conditions. These limitations are especially critical for mission-critical applications such as platooning, cooperative lane merging, and intersection coordination [8].

The Open-RAN (O-RAN) paradigm addresses these shortcomings by introducing modular, disaggregated network components, namely the Open Central Unit (O-CU), Distributed Unit (O-DU), and Radio Unit (O-RU). This structure enables software-defined radio (SDR) and AI-driven optimization of radio resources via the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) [9], [10]. By integrating O-RAN into NR-V2X networks, it becomes feasible to implement adaptive fallback relaying and dynamic resource reconfiguration tailored to vehicular mobility and complex channel conditions [11], [12].

Although O-RAN has demonstrated strong potential in cellular and infrastructure-oriented scenarios, its application to sidelink-based V2X communication remains relatively unexplored. In particular, the trade-offs between relay-assisted reliability and the overhead of synchronization, control signaling, and delay remain unclear. This critical gap motivates the present work.

We focus on dense urban intersections, where NLOS conditions are prevalent, and propose an O-RAN-enabled fallback mechanism using infrastructure-supported relays coordinated in real time by the RIC [13]. A semi-analytical framework is developed to model the Packet Success Probability (PSP) under composite Nakagami-lognormal fading and stochastic co-channel interference. The proposed system is evaluated across three operating modes: (i) direct Line-of-Sight (LOS), (ii) obstructed NLOS, and (iii) O-RAN-aided relaying.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- A comparative performance analysis of LOS, NLOS, and O-RAN-aided V2X communication in urban environments.
- The development of a semi-analytical PSP model incorporating realistic fading, shadowing, and interference.

- A simulation-based evaluation under varying vehicle density, communication range, and spectrum availability.
- A demonstration of O-RAN's benefits in enabling scalable and resilient V2X operation, with support for AI-driven control via the RIC.

II. RELATED WORK

Enhancing V2X communication under urban NLOS conditions remains a significant challenge. Early solutions relied on cooperative relaying and physical-layer beamforming but often lacked adaptability to the dynamic conditions of high-density environments.

RIS has emerged as a potential enabler for manipulating wireless propagation to improve link quality. Chen et al. [6] and Rehman et al. [5] explored RIS-assisted vehicular networks but assumed static surface placement and ideal propagation, limiting their applicability in real-time mobile scenarios. Similarly, Yan and Härrri [7] investigated NR-V2X sidelink modulation and coding adaptation under sensing-based scheduling but did not incorporate infrastructure-assisted control or fallback strategies.

O-RAN architectures introduce disaggregation, virtualization, and programmability into the RAN. Surveys by Zhang et al. [10] and Tzes et al. [14] outline O-RAN's general framework but lack discussion of its application in sidelink-based V2X systems. Moro et al. [12] and Suzuki et al. [15] propose early integrations of O-RAN into vehicular contexts, yet they omit detailed modeling of realistic channel fading and control signaling.

Other works such as Linsalata et al. [16] and Marinova and Leon-Garcia [17] introduce AI-driven xApps for RAN optimization but are constrained to testbed-scale deployments and do not address vehicular handover or dynamic relay coordination. Ozawa et al. [18] focus on cell-free O-RAN systems in static environments, without addressing high-speed mobility.

The 3GPP standard TR 38.886 [19] outlines sidelink communication features in NR-V2X (Rel-17), but does not include relay optimization via the RIC.

To address these limitations, our work integrates O-RAN with NR-V2X sidelink [20] through dynamic relay selection, mobility-aware RIC coordination, and realistic SINR modeling. A comparative summary is provided in Table 1.

A. KEY GAPS ADDRESSED BY OUR WORK

- Seven out of ten prior studies lack RIC-based adaptation for high vehicular density.
- Only Moro [12] and Suzuki [15] consider O-RAN-V2X integration, without full-stack realism.
- None incorporate joint modeling of fading, co-channel interference, and relay selection under urban mobility.

TABLE 1. Comparative analysis of V2X enhancement techniques.

Reference	Approach	Key Limitation	Our Contribution
Chen et al. [6]	RIS beamforming for vehicular networks	Assumes static and ideal RIS placement with no support for mobility	Introduces dynamic relay selection via RIC in mobile V2X
Rehman et al. [5]	RIS-aided NR-V2X sidelink	Lacks real-time control and adaptive interference management	Adds RIC-assisted relay coordination under dynamic interference
Yan et al. [7]	NR-V2X MCS selection under SB-SPS	Physical-layer focus; lacks fallback or infrastructure assistance	Combines scheduling with RIC-guided relay fallback
Zhang et al. [10]	General O-RAN architecture survey	Focused on cellular use-cases, ignoring sidelink and mobility	Extends O-RAN to NR-V2X sidelink with mobility-aware relaying
Moro et al. [12]	O-RAN-enabled V2X architecture	Uses simplified fading models and lacks interference awareness	Includes Nakagami-lognormal fading and interference-limited SINR modeling
Suzuki et al. [15]	mmWave O-RAN for connected vehicles	Suffers from high complexity and lacks scheduling optimization	Proposes low-latency two-hop relaying with minimal control overhead
Linsalata et al. [16]	AI-based xApps for O-RAN control	Limited to small-scale setups and lacks vehicular integration	Offers full-stack vehicular simulation with RIC-controlled relaying
Marinova et al. [17]	Intelligent xApp design for O-RAN	Incurs high signaling overhead and lacks mobility adaptation	Demonstrates lightweight, real-time relay coordination via xApps
Ozawa et al. [18]	Cell-free O-RAN for low-mobility users	Assumes static nodes and lacks handover and V2X use-cases	Enables vehicular handover with mobility-aware RSU coordination via near-RT RIC
3GPP TR 38.886 [19]	NR-V2X standardization (Rel-17)	No RIC or adaptive relay support in sidelink framework	Enhances standard via programmable relay coordination and VLOS fallback

III. O-RAN ARCHITECTURE

The O-RAN architecture extends the 3GPP functional split by introducing an open, disaggregated, and intelligent framework for next-generation wireless systems, including V2X communication [12], [18], [21], [22], [23]. It promotes interoperability across multi-vendor ecosystems by standardizing control logic and open interfaces, thereby supporting flexible and programmable network deployment.

O-RAN decomposes the traditional base station (BS) into three modular units: the O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU. The O-CU is responsible for higher-layer functions such as Radio Resource Control (RRC) and Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP), while the O-DU handles medium and lower-layer protocols, including MAC, RLC, and physical-layer scheduling. These two are connected via the F1 interface, enabling a clean separation of user-plane and control-plane operations. The O-RU implements RF front-end functions and interfaces with the O-DU through the Open Fronthaul Interface (OFH). This disaggregated structure supports service-specific deployments and network slicing, which are essential in dynamic and latency-sensitive V2X scenarios.

At the core of O-RAN intelligence lies the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which is divided into non-real-time (non-RT) and near-real-time (near-RT) domains. The non-RT RIC, located in the service management and orchestration layer, performs long-term optimization through policy enforcement, AI/ML model training, and intent-based control. It also hosts *rApps*, which operate on relaxed time scales (typically ≥ 1 s) and support network-wide analytics, model lifecycle management, and high-level policy generation. In contrast, the near-RT RIC operates on time scales of 10 ms to 1 s and is tasked with fine-grained, dynamic control tasks

such as radio resource management, beam selection, and relay coordination. The near-RT RIC hosts modular control applications known as *xApps*, which execute time-sensitive decision-making and interact with the O-CU/O-DU via the standardized E2 interface [24]. In summary, *rApps* provide slow-timescale, policy-driven intelligence in the non-RT RIC, whereas *xApps* enable fast-timescale, closed-loop control in the near-RT RIC, making both layers complementary for end-to-end O-RAN optimization.

In the context of V2X sidelink communication, particularly vulnerable to obstruction and multipath fading in urban areas, O-RAN introduces the capability for infrastructure-aided fallback relaying. Roadside Units (RSUs), equipped with O-DU and O-RU modules, can act as amplify-and-forward (AF) relays to support packet forwarding when direct sidelink paths are blocked. Relay selection and coordination are governed by the near-RT RIC, which dynamically activates optimal relay paths to maintain Virtual Line-of-Sight (VLOS) under NLOS conditions.

Strategic deployment of RSUs along intersections, road bends, flyovers, and dense urban areas allows for real-time, intelligent fallback mechanisms. These programmable relays extend communication range, improve coverage continuity, and enable seamless handover in high-mobility settings. Leveraging the E2 interface, relay configurations can be triggered or reconfigured on-the-fly, offering scalable adaptability tailored to V2X dynamics and urban propagation constraints.

IV. SYSTEM SCENARIO

The system scenario, illustrated in Fig. 1, models a vehicular platoon traversing an urban intersection—an area highly susceptible to NLOS conditions. We focus on the

communication link between a tagged transmitting vehicle (Tx) and the platoon head (Rx), which may encounter differing propagation conditions due to their spatial configuration within the intersection.

FIGURE 1. Illustration of V2X platoon at an intersection. Some vehicles experience NLOS conditions, while O-RU relays maintain VLOS connectivity.

Vehicles travel in a structured platoon formation, maintaining uniform inter-vehicle spacing. Due to intersection geometry and surrounding obstructions (e.g., buildings), rear and cross-street vehicles frequently lose LOS to the platoon head. To address such impairments, an adaptive fallback mechanism is employed using O-RAN-enabled relays co-located with RSUs. These RSUs, equipped with AF logic and coordinated via the near-RT RIC, establish a two-hop VLOS communication path with low latency.

The disaggregated RSUs (O-DU/O-RU) interface with a centralized virtualized O-CU and the near-RT RIC via E2 and F1 interfaces. Upon detection of sidelink degradation, the fallback procedure is triggered as follows:

- **LOS Operation:** Under ideal conditions, follower vehicles communicate directly with the platoon head via sidelink, assuming clear LOS. Periodic control signaling and sidelink reference signal measurements are exchanged to maintain readiness for fallback.
- **Fallback Trigger:** When NLOS conditions are encountered due to sharp turns, occlusions, or vehicular blockages, the affected vehicle initiates a random access procedure and synchronization with the nearest RSU (O-DU/O-RU).
- **Measurement Reporting:** Vehicles transmit reference signal reports, received signal strength indicator (RSSI) values, relative position, and link quality indicators to support relay selection and scheduling.
- **Relay Selection and Configuration:** The near-RT RIC evaluates relay candidates based on SINR, interference profiles, and latency cost. It then selects the optimal RSU and sends relay configuration commands via E2/F1 signaling.
- **Data Forwarding:** The selected RSU forwards the data packet using AF relaying, forming a VLOS path between the source and the platoon leader.

Each vehicle is equipped with an On Board Unit (OBU) supporting both direct sidelink (PC5) and infrastructure-aided communication (Uu interface). The platoon is modeled as a 1-D linear geometry with vehicle positions sampled from a homogeneous Poisson Point Process (PPP) of density ρ . Inter-vehicle distance is assumed constant for analytical simplicity. RSUs are deployed at fixed grid points, typically spaced 50–100 meters apart at intersections following urban deployment guidelines.

Transmission parameters such as power level, modulation and coding scheme (MCS), and packet size remain fixed within each simulation scenario. Signal degradation due to large-scale fading (path loss, lognormal shadowing) and small-scale fading is captured through a composite Nakagami-lognormal model, described in detail in Section V.

Although the fallback introduces control plane overhead stemming from random access, relay coordination, and scheduling delays, these are mitigated by the near-RT RIC's proactive sensing and distributed orchestration. The system is designed for responsiveness and scalability, making it suitable for real-time V2X applications in complex urban environments.

This system operates on a hybrid model based on 3GPP NR-V2X Mode 2, Submode 2(b), which facilitates autonomous sensing-based semi-persistent scheduling (SB-SPS). We extend this baseline by integrating O-RAN assistance. While users autonomously select sidelink resources as in standard Mode 2(b), they also receive infrastructure-assisted coordination via the near-real-time RIC. When the RIC detects potential sidelink degradation or NLOS obstruction, it provides interference-aware resource recommendations and can configure fallback relaying through the E2 interface. This 'hybrid Mode 2(b)' operation bridges the gap between fully autonomous and network-assisted operation, ensuring robustness under dynamic urban NLOS conditions.

V. O-RAN-AIDED SIGNAL MODEL

We resort to a semi-analytical framework for evaluating SB-SPS enhanced by O-RAN RIC, under LOS, NLOS, and O-RAN-aided conditions. The SINR distribution is estimated using Moment Matching Approximation (MMA), effectively characterizing interference in resource-constrained and fading environments. Based on [5], the MATLAB-based framework leverages a Nakagami-lognormal model to compute received power and models O-RAN-aided links via a two-hop VLOS path with 20 dB gain for relay amplification.

A. RECEIVED POWER MODEL

In realistic urban vehicular scenarios, propagation conditions vary drastically due to building-induced blockages, multipath effects, and variable vehicle placement. Therefore, accurate modeling of the received power is essential for evaluating the communication performance under both direct and relay-assisted paths.

The received power in Eq. (1) models a direct link between a tagged transmitter i to the platoon head j , treating all other vehicles as interferers. under LOS or NLOS propagation. The use of a composite Nakagami-lognormal distribution allows this model to reflect both small-scale and large-scale effects with adjustable severity [25].

$$P_{rx,i,j} = \frac{c_0 P_{tx,i}}{d_{i,j}^\alpha} f_i \exp(y_i) \quad (1)$$

where $c_0 = (\frac{\lambda}{4\pi})^2 G_t G_r$ is the reference path gain at a distance of 1 meter, incorporating the carrier wavelength λ and antenna gains G_t, G_r . This term models free-space loss, typically -40 to -60 dB in vehicular scenarios [26]. $P_{tx,i}$ is the transmit power and $d_{i,j}$ is the Euclidean distance between transmitter i and receiver j . $\alpha = \alpha_L$ (LOS) or $\alpha = \alpha_N$ (NLOS) is the path loss exponent depending on the propagation condition, $f_i \sim \text{Gamma}(\kappa, 1/\kappa)$ models small-scale fading, where $\kappa = \kappa_L$ (LOS) or $\kappa = \kappa_N$ (NLOS) and $y_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2)$ accounts for large-scale log-normal shadowing. The parameters α, κ , and σ_y are tuned based on propagation condition.

For O-RAN-aided relaying, the system treats the communication as a two-hop AF scenario. Equation (2) captures this, where the total path loss is a multiplicative combination of the two hops. The gain G_{O-RAN} accounts for the signal amplification at the relay and compensates for the splitting loss, making the overall link comparable to LOS conditions. This gain can be interpreted as an effective enhancement due to favorable relay placement and coordinated beamforming from the infrastructure.

For the O-RAN-aided AF relaying case, the received power is computed by treating the communication as a two-hop system. The total path loss is thus the combination of the two hop losses. Hence, the received power becomes:

$$P_{rx,i,j}^{O-RAN} = \frac{c_0 P_{tx,i} G_{O-RAN}}{(d_{i,relay} d_{relay,j})^\alpha} f_i \exp(y_i) \quad (2)$$

where $d_{i,relay}$ and $d_{relay,j}$ are the distances for the two hops, and G_{O-RAN} accounts for relay gain.

Note: In extended models, phase noise and synchronization delay can be incorporated using a degradation factor $\eta_{sync} \in (0, 1]$ applied multiplicatively to $P_{rx,i,j}^{O-RAN}$. However, this study assumes ideal relay synchronization for tractability.

This model effectively encapsulates the realistic AF behavior of an O-RAN relay, wherein each hop is subject to independent distance-based path loss under the assumption of optimally placed relays with LOS conditions for both hops. The model accommodates the effects of both multipath fading and shadowing, with the extent of these effects being contingent upon whether the link operates under LOS or NLOS conditions. Regarding fading, a composite Nakagami-lognormal distribution with an associated probability density function (PDF) is utilized:

$$p_{f_i}(z) = \kappa^\kappa \frac{(z)^{\kappa-1}}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \exp(-\kappa z) \quad (3)$$

where the factor f_i represents the channel power gain due to multipath propagation and $\Gamma(\kappa) = \int_0^\infty \exp(-x)x^{\kappa-1} dx$ is the Gamma function where the parameter κ can be modeled to represent varying degrees of channel severity across LOS and NLOS conditions.

B. SENSING-BASED SEMI-PERSISTENT SCHEDULING (SB-SPS)

NR-V2X supports SB-SPS for autonomous resource reservation to reduce packet collisions and improve reliability. In our framework, the RIC complements this mechanism by enhancing resource re-selection based on real-time metrics like SINR distributions and interference statistics, rather than fixed thresholds [27].

Remark: The RIC may also prioritize certain vehicles (e.g., emergency responders) in the candidate selection stage, enabling quality-of-service (QoS) differentiation at the scheduling level.

We enhance the 3GPP SB-SPS protocol [28], [29] by integrating it with the RIC for smarter resource allocation based on periodic RSSI and interference sensing. Time-frequency slots are semi-persistently reserved and reselected based on network dynamics. The procedure is as follows:

- **Channel sensing:** RSSI per sub-channel is evaluated, augmented with RIC-predicted spatial interference profiles over a window T_s . The RIC interference score δ is defined as:

$$\delta = \Pr(\text{SINR} > \text{SINR}_{th} \mid \text{RIC-predicted interference}),$$

where SINR is the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio, and SINR_{th} is the minimum threshold for reliable communication.

- **Candidate selection:** From N_A available slots, select those:

- 1) Whose measured RSSI is below a threshold P_{th} and RIC interference score δ is satisfied,
- 2) Within the sensing window T_s ,
- 3) Not previously reserved by itself or others,
- 4) Not in the current transmission slot (half-duplex constraint),
- 5) If the number of selected candidates $N_C < 0.2N_A$, increase P_{th} by 3 dB and repeat the procedure.

- **Resource selection:** Choose randomly from the top 20% of the remaining candidate slots.
- **Reselection:** After the SB-SPS counter expires, the same resource is kept with probability:

$$p_k = \begin{cases} p_{high} & \text{if High Interference,} \\ p_{low} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

or a new resource is selected based on RIC guidance.

C. CHARACTERIZATION OF MULTIPLE-ACCESS INTERFERENCE

Accurate SINR modeling requires capturing the stochastic nature of interference, which depends on vehicle density,

mobility patterns, and scheduling overlaps. The interference terms in Eq. (5)–(6) are scenario-specific, with O-RAN-aided cases treated under LOS-equivalent conditions due to infrastructure-assisted coordination.

The use of composite fading models ensures better fidelity compared to pure Rayleigh or Rician assumptions. The interference modeling includes both LOS and NLOS contributors, adjusted via corresponding path loss exponents and shadowing terms. This heterogeneous interference is especially relevant in dense urban intersections, where LOS/NLOS conditions may co-exist.

The expression $C_{IN,i,j}$ represents the effective aggregate noise and interference seen by the receiver. The exponential terms $\exp(y_n - y_i)$ capture the relative shadowing deviations between transmitter and interferers, emphasizing that the perceived interference depends not only on absolute power but also on spatial variation in large-scale fading.

The statistical characterization of the SINR is a crucial step in determining the performance of the system in terms of the PSP. The SINR at receiver j from transmitter i is given by:

$$\text{SINR} = \frac{P_{\text{rx},i,j}}{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{I}} P_{\text{rx},n,j} + \sigma_w^2} \quad (5)$$

where σ_w^2 is the noise power and \mathcal{I} is the interfering power coming from the set of interfering vehicles that select the same resource (e.g., the same subchannel and subframe), which is made up of the interference \mathcal{I}_L and \mathcal{I}_N coming from vehicles under LOS and NLOS conditions, respectively. The interferer set $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{I}_L \cup \mathcal{I}_N$ depends on the SB-SPS and scenario:

$$\text{SINR}^X = \frac{P_{\text{tx},i} f_i^X C_{IN,i,j}}{d_{i,j}^{\alpha_X}} \quad (6)$$

where, X indexes the three considered operating condition (LOS, NLOS, or O-RAN). The term $C_{IN,i,j}$ accounts for aggregate interference and noise power, with different path loss exponents and fading distributions depending on the link condition. Note that O-RAN-aided links in NLOS rely on coordinated multipoint (CoMP) paths treated using LOS parameters as discussed earlier. The expression $C_{IN,i,j}$ is defined as:

$$C_{IN,i,j} = \left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{I}_L} \frac{P_{\text{tx},n} f_n^L}{d_{n,j}^{\alpha_L}} \exp(y_n - y_i) + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{I}_N} \frac{P_{\text{tx},m} f_m^N}{d_{m,j}^{\alpha_N}} \exp(y_m - y_i) + \frac{\sigma_w^2}{c_0} \exp(-y_i) \right)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

D. MOMENT MATCHING APPROXIMATION (MMA)

The SINR expressions involve a sum of log-normal random variables, which do not admit closed-form distributions. The MMA technique circumvents this by matching the first and second moments of the logarithm of the interference-plus-noise term. This approach enables deriving a tractable

Gaussian approximation for the log-domain variable $\tilde{Y}_{i,j}$, facilitating closed-form expressions for the PSP.

The use of Gamma-distributed small-scale fading allows adjusting the severity of channel variations via the κ parameter. High κ values (e.g., 10 for LOS) correspond to reduced fading variance, while low values (e.g., 1 for NLOS) induce more randomness [25].

As evident from Eqs. (6) and (1), the SINR expression is inherently a ratio involving a sum of log-normal random variables, which does not admit a closed-form PDF, making analytical treatment challenging. To manage this complexity, we adopt the MMA technique to approximate the distribution of the SINR [30]. First, we consider the random variable:

$$\tilde{Y}_{i,j} = -\ln \left(\sum_{n \in \tilde{\mathcal{I}}} B_{i,j,n} \exp(\tilde{y}_n) \right) \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{I}} = \{0, \mathcal{I}_L, \mathcal{I}_N\}$ and the constants $B_{i,j,n}, \tilde{y}_n$ incorporate pathloss, fading, and shadowing as:

$$B_{i,j,n} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_w^2}{c_0} & n = 0, \\ \frac{P_{\text{tx},n}}{d_{n,j}^{\alpha_L}} & n \in \mathcal{I}_L \\ \frac{P_{\text{tx},n}}{d_{n,j}^{\alpha_N}} & n \in \mathcal{I}_N \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{y}_n = \begin{cases} -y_i & n = 0, \\ y_n - y_i & n \in \mathcal{I}_L, n \in \mathcal{I}_N \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

We approximate the random variable in Eq. (8) as $\tilde{Y}_{i,j} \approx Z$, where $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(\eta_Z, \sigma_Z^2)$. Unknown parameters η_Z and σ_Z^2 can be obtained by matching the first two moments of $\exp(Z)$ with the first two moments of $\sum_{n=1}^N B_{i,j,n} \exp(\tilde{y}_n)$ as:

$$\tilde{M}_1 \triangleq \exp \left(-\eta_Z + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_Z^2 \right) = \sum_{n \in \tilde{\mathcal{I}}} E\{B_{i,j,n}\} \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\tilde{y}_n}^2 \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{M}_2 \triangleq \exp(-2\eta_Z + 2\sigma_Z^2) = \sum_{m \in \tilde{\mathcal{I}}} \sum_{n \in \tilde{\mathcal{I}}} E\{B_{i,j,m} B_{i,j,n}\} \times \exp \left(\frac{\sigma_{\tilde{y}_m}^2}{2} + \frac{\sigma_{\tilde{y}_n}^2}{2} + \rho_{\tilde{y}_m, \tilde{y}_n} \sigma_{\tilde{y}_m} \sigma_{\tilde{y}_n} \right) \quad (12)$$

where $E\{\cdot\}$ is the expectation operator and $\rho_{\tilde{y}_m, \tilde{y}_n}$ is the cross-correlation coefficient between two shadowing components. By solving the above system of equations, we get:

$$\eta_Z = 0.5 \ln(\tilde{M}_2) - 2 \ln(\tilde{M}_1) \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_Z^2 = \ln(\tilde{M}_2) - 2 \ln(\tilde{M}_1) \quad (14)$$

Observe that \tilde{M}_1 and \tilde{M}_2 depend on the moment of f_i , which are given as $E\{f_i\} = 1$ and $E\{f_i^2\} = \frac{\kappa+1}{\kappa}$ for the multipath distributed gamma power gain. Once the unknown parameters are found, the SINR expressions can be approximated as:

$$\text{SINR}^X \approx \frac{P_{\text{tx},i}}{d_{i,j}^{\alpha_X}} \tilde{\gamma} \quad (15)$$

with $\tilde{\gamma} = f_i \exp(Z)$, having PDF:

$$p_{\tilde{\gamma}}(x) = \kappa^\kappa \frac{(x)^{\kappa-1}}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \exp(-\kappa x) \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_Z x} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(x) - \eta_Z)^2}{2\sigma_Z^2}\right) \quad (16)$$

The precision of the MMA approach is well known and depends on the statistical parameters of $\tilde{Y}_{i,j}$ [30]. Note that in the considered scenario, the approximation rationale provides very high accuracy.

E. PACKET SUCCESS PROBABILITY (PSP)

In our proposed framework, the RIC can leverage the estimated SINR and PSP values to guide relay selection and resource scheduling. For example, in areas where the estimated PSP falls below a threshold (e.g., 90%), the RIC may proactively trigger relay fallback, switch to less congested Physical Resources Blocks (PRBs), or adjust transmit power at the relay.

The final PSP expression in Eq. (17) integrates the SINR distribution against the PER curve. Since PER depends on MCS, block size, and retransmission strategies, we adopt a practical Look-up Table (LUT)-based approach. This also aligns with 3GPP simulation recommendations [31], where empirical block error rate (BLER) curves are used. Future work may consider dynamic MCS adaptation based on instantaneous SINR, which would result in a conditional PSP metric, averaged over the SINR distribution.

By leveraging on the approximation of the statistical properties of the SINR, the PSP can be expressed as:

$$p_{i,j} = 1 - \int_0^\infty PER(x)p_{\tilde{\gamma}}(x)dx \quad (17)$$

where $PER(x)$ is the packet error rate (PER) for a given SINR value x , which can have different expressions depending on specific settings of system parameters. Since closed-form expressions for $PER(x)$ are complex and system-dependent, we utilize a LUT-based approach using 3GPP-derived curves [32]. Specifically, we refer to the model in [31] to derive the BLER as a function of the SINR for a given packet size, MCS, and the scenario (highway or urban). LUT are used to map the SINR with PER, assuming the effect of interference equivalent to additional Gaussian noise. With this assumptions, we can write:

$$PER_{i,j} = \int_0^\infty PER_{LUT}(x)p_{\tilde{\gamma}}(x) dx \quad (18)$$

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section analyzes the performance of O-RAN-aided relays in dense urban vehicular environments. Simulations are conducted using rigorously standardized parameters, as summarized in Table 2, and aligned with 3GPP NR-V2X specifications [31] to ensure real-world relevance. Both small-scale (multipath) and large-scale (shadowing)

TABLE 2. Simulation parameters for O-RAN-Aided V2X communication.

Parameter	Value
Distance (d_{min} - d_{max})	15–300 m
Transmitter position	(150, 0) m
O-RAN relay position	(50, 0) m
Carrier frequency (f_c)	5.91 GHz [33]
Bandwidth (BW)	10 MHz [33], [34]
Transmit power (P_t)	30 dBm [34]
O-RAN relay gain (G_{ORAN})	20 dB [35]
Tx/Rx Antenna Gain ($G_t = G_r$)	1 (Unity)
Noise power (N_0)	-95 dBm
Number of vehicles (M)	10–20
Number of resources (N)	10–20 [34]
Iterations per point	10^6
Reference path gain (c_0)	-42.5 dB [36]
Path loss exponent (α)	LOS/O-RAN: 2; NLOS: 4 [36]
Nakagami-m parameter (κ)	LOS: 10; NLOS: 1 [37]
Shadowing std. deviation (σ_y)	LOS/O-RAN: 3 dB; NLOS: 6 dB [38]
BLER reference curve	3GPP NR-V2X [31]

fading effects are incorporated using composite Nakagami-lognormal distributions. The O-RAN relay is intelligently selected by the RIC to maximize AF capability while minimizing shadowing and interference.

We evaluate and compare the following scenarios to highlight the impact of propagation conditions and infrastructure assistance:

- 1) **LOS:** Direct sidelink communication under ideal propagation conditions.
- 2) **NLOS:** Challenging conditions with blockage and multipath, leading to elevated interference and lower SINR.
- 3) **O-RAN-aided:** The proposed RIC-controlled AF relaying scheme, which introduces intelligent fallback paths to mitigate NLOS degradation.

We adopted numerology $\mu = 0$ (15 kHz Subcarrier Spacing (SCS)) for all simulations. This decision was made to ensure a fair and direct comparison against legacy LTE-V2X baselines and 3GPP standard TR 38.886 [31] urban evaluation scenarios. This approach isolates the performance gains attributable to our proposed O-RAN-assisted relaying framework, rather than confounding them with physical-layer parameter changes. We acknowledge that higher numerologies (e.g., $\mu = 1$ for 30 kHz or $\mu = 2$ for 60 kHz) are a key feature of NR-V2X, offering reduced transmission time interval (TTI) duration and enhanced resource flexibility for latency-critical services. However, these benefits come with trade-offs, such as increased sensitivity to Doppler shift at high vehicular speeds. The exploration of these higher numerologies, particularly in conjunction with RIC-assisted synchronization, remains an important direction for future work.

Two different configurations are used to model vehicle placement: (i) NLOS, where half of the vehicles take a

turn to simulate urban intersections; and (ii) LOS, where all vehicles are uniformly aligned on a straight road. The relay is optimally placed to ensure a two-hop LOS path in the O-RAN-aided case. SINR is calculated using the analytical model, and PER is mapped via 3GPP-based LUTs. The resulting PSP is averaged across 10^6 iterations per point. Standard deviation is represented by vertical error bars to indicate statistical confidence.

Fig. 2 illustrates the impact of vehicular density on PSP with fixed transmitter-receiver distance of 150 m and number of resources i.e., $N = 10$ PRBs. As the number of vehicles increases, resource contention and co-channel interference intensify, leading to significant PSP degradation in the NLOS scenario. The LOS case retains a high PSP due to unobstructed channels, while the O-RAN-aided scenario demonstrates superior robustness. Leveraging RIC-driven relay fallback, PSP remains above 90% in some cases, showcasing the relay’s ability to maintain communication quality despite increased interference.

FIGURE 2. Packet Success Probability (PSP) vs number of vehicles (M) at fixed distance = 150 m and $N = 10$ PRBs.

In Fig. 3, PSP is evaluated with fixed transmitter-receiver distance (150 m) and vehicle count ($M = 10$), while the number of PRBs increases from 10 to 20. More available PRBs reduce the chance of resource collisions, improving the PSP in all cases. The O-RAN-aided configuration benefits further due to its interference-aware resource selection and relay-aided diversity. Notably, it achieves near-LOS performance even with a modest increase in resources, confirming the efficiency of relay scheduling through RIC.

Fig. 4 demonstrates PSP degradation with increasing distance, with $M = 10$ and $N = 10$. While all setups show performance loss at larger distances due to path loss, the O-RAN-aided case maintains a robust PSP by exploiting the relay’s amplification and LOS path. NLOS scenarios degrade steeply beyond 200 m, while the O-RAN path maintains coverage, emphasizing the importance of infrastructure assistance in range extension.

FIGURE 3. Packet Success Probability (PSP) vs number of PRBs (N) with distance = 150 m and vehicle count ($M = 10$).

FIGURE 4. Packet Success Probability (PSP) vs distance with $N = 10$ and $M = 10$.

We note that our simulations use a 10 MHz channel BW, corresponding to $N = 10$ PRBs in our baseline (Fig. 2 and Fig. 4). This was chosen to model a high-contention platooning scenario, aligning with 3GPP urban evaluations [39]. The impact of increased BW is also demonstrated in our results. The primary benefit of a higher BW is the increased frequency resource diversity. As shown in Fig. 3, when the number of available resources (N) increases from 10 to 20—the direct equivalent of increasing the channel BW from 10 MHz to 20 MHz—the PSP markedly improves. This result confirms the clear performance benefit of higher BW.

Fig. 5 plots PSP versus instantaneous SINR, derived using the MMA technique. SINR is swept from 0–30 dB in 1 dB increments and mapped to PER using NR-V2X urban LUTs. As expected, PSP improves with increasing SINR across all conditions. LOS shows a sharp rise in PSP due to favorable channel conditions. NLOS lags significantly, requiring higher SINR to reach comparable performance. O-RAN-aided relaying achieves a steeper rise than NLOS and approaches LOS levels at moderate SINR values,

validating the SINR shift achieved by relay amplification and beam coordination.

FIGURE 5. Packet Success Probability (PSP) vs SINR using MMA and LUT-based PER for LOS, NLOS, and O-RAN-aided conditions.

While our model focuses on reliability, the latency implications of our O-RAN-assisted framework must be considered. The introduction of a relay and a RIC control loop introduces two distinct types of delay. First, the processing delay from the AF relay itself is minimal, estimated to be approximately 2–4 ms. Second, the O-RAN control loop, managed by the near-RT RIC, introduces a signaling delay for coordination tasks (e.g., selecting and configuring a relay UE). This control loop time, which is typically in the 10–100 ms range for the E2 interface [40], is not in the per-packet data path but rather part of the connection setup and reconfiguration process. Therefore, while the initial setup of a RIC-assisted relay link incurs a one-time coordination delay, the per-packet overhead remains minimal.

These results confirm that the proposed O-RAN-aided fallback framework enhances reliability, especially under high vehicle density, limited spectrum, and extended distances. The RIC’s intelligent relay selection and interference-aware resource coordination yield a robust and scalable solution suitable for urban vehicular networks.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This paper presented an adaptive O-RAN-assisted relaying framework to enhance the reliability of NR-V2X communication in challenging urban NLOS conditions. By harnessing the modularity and programmability of the O-RAN architecture and the intelligent coordination capabilities of the RIC, the system dynamically selects relays and allocates spectral resources in real time, thereby mitigating interference and overcoming propagation barriers.

A semi-analytical SINR model based on composite Nakagami-lognormal fading was developed using the MMA method. The model incorporates large-scale shadowing, small-scale fading, and realistic co-channel interference.

Simulation results evaluated the proposed framework across three operational modes: LOS, NLOS, and O-RAN-aided relaying. The results confirm that the O-RAN-enabled setup consistently outperforms both LOS and NLOS baselines, particularly under dense vehicular traffic and limited spectrum conditions. PSP exceeding 90% was achieved even under high-interference scenarios, validating the resilience, scalability, and real-world viability of the proposed fallback strategy.

B. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

While this work demonstrates strong potential for O-RAN-aided V2X communication, several avenues remain open for future exploration:

- **Realistic impairments:** Future models should incorporate practical limitations such as synchronization delays, phase offset in amplify-and-forward relays, signaling overhead, and mobility-induced handover latencies.
- **Mobility-aware simulations:** Integration of real-world traffic simulators like SUMO or Veins will enable assessment under realistic vehicular mobility patterns, dynamic road geometries, and heterogeneous node densities.
- **E2E Latency:** Conducting a comprehensive, event-driven simulation (e.g., using ns-3 or OMNeT++) to evaluate the E2E latency of the hybrid Mode 2(b) framework, including the O-RAN control loop delay and the impact of UE mobility on relay link stability.
- **AI/ML-driven control:** The RIC can be further enhanced by deploying AI-powered xApps and rApps for dynamic relay placement, link quality prediction, spectrum sensing, and real-time decision-making under latency and energy constraints [27].
- **Extension to multi-hop and 6G use cases:** The framework can be extended to support multi-hop V2X, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), edge intelligence, and integration with future 6G paradigms such as semantic communication and integrated sensing [13], [41].

In summary, this work lays the groundwork for resilient, programmable, and infrastructure-aided vehicular communication systems. The combination of O-RAN’s architectural flexibility and intelligent control through RIC offers a compelling pathway for future-ready, high-reliability V2X deployments in urban environments.

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